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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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APPRAISING THE JURISDICTION OF THE COURT AND COMPETITION AND CONSUMER PROTECTION TRIBUNAL IN PROSECUTING ELECTRICITY CONSUMER COMPLAINTS IN NIGERIA

By

Alfred M. Tijah* and Kwaghkehe Ierkwagh**

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ABSTRACT

The Nigerian electric power sector prior to the year 2005 was wholly under the Federal Government of Nigeria's vertically integrated national utility company called the National Electric Power Authority (NEPA). NEPA with monopoly over the power sector was then the sole electricity service provider. Consequently, the adjudicatory jurisdiction for redressing electricity consumer complaints arising from the administrative actions and decisions of NEPA was squarely within the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court (FHC) by virtue of section 251(1)(r) of the Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended). With the enactment of Electric Power Sector Reform Act, 2005 which led to the unbundling and privatisation of the power sector, the exclusive jurisdiction of the FHC over service provisions to electricity consumer were consequentially altered. There now exist at least three main adjudicatory bodies with jurisdiction for redressing electricity consumer issues: the FHC, States High Courts and the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT). This paper employed doctrinal research methodology in assessing the extent of the jurisdiction for redressing electricity consumer injustices in Nigeria. It found that, adjudicatory powers of the CCPT are essentially a usurpation of the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court. Also, though special tribunals like the CCPT are created for a cheap, simple and expeditious redressal process, however, approaching the CCPT involves certain condition precedents that are procedurally lengthy and time consuming. A constitutional amendment becomes apposite to bring the CCPT in line with constitutionalism and streamline its adjudicatory process for speedy dispensation of justice.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Electricity is the driver of meaningful development in any economy. The generation and supply of sufficient electricity for meaningful development is, however, cost-effective and usually undertaken by monopolies that tend to abuse their monopoly position. In Nigeria, the supply of electricity was the exclusive preserve of the National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) from 1973-2005. During the reign of NEPA, the power sector was in a very deplorable state and experienced negative growth in connection rates, power generation, regulation, and capital investments.¹ Consumer satisfaction was relegated and the law granted NEPA immunity against payment of damages to electricity consumers for loss or damages caused as a result of the poor and dangerous services rendered.²

The Electric Power Sector Reform Act, (EPSR Act) 2005 upon its enactment provided the legal framework which led to the unbundling and privatisation of the power sector into eighteen (18) successor companies which took over the responsibilities of electricity generation, transmission and distribution from NEPA through a holding company known as the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN).³ The 18 autonomous companies comprised of six (6) generating companies,⁴ one (1) transmission company,⁵ and eleven (11) distribution companies.⁶

Though the Nigerian electricity supply industry has been unbundled into several companies and privatised, yet it maintains a monopoly situation. This has been made possible with the grant of exclusive franchise to each of the eleven (11) distribution companies to undertake the supply of electricity to specified areas in Nigerian without

¹ Alfred M Tijah, 'The Role of the Minister of Power in Nigeria Electric Power Sector Reform: A Legal Perspective' *Law Digest* (Lagos, issue 29 Winter 2022) 16.

² NEPA Act 1990, s12.

³ *NEPA v Omotosho and Ors* (2010) LPELR-4579 (CA) at 8 per Raphael Chikwe Agbo JCA; Alfred M Tijah, 'Periscoping Competition in the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry' *U.I Law Journal* (2023) (13) 176; Victor Okolobah and Zuhaimy Ismail, 'On the Issues, Challenges and Prospects of Electricity Power Sector in Nigeria' (2013) (2)(6) *International Journal of Economy, Management and Social Sciences* 413.

⁴ The six (6) generation companies (GENCOs) are (1) Afam Power Plc (2) Egbin Power Plc (3) Kainji/ Jebba Hydro Electric Plc (4) Sapele Power Plc (5) Shiroro Hydro Electric Plc (6) Ughelli Power Plc.

⁵ Called the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN).

⁶ The eleven (11) distribution companies (DISCOs) are (1) Abuja Distribution Company (2) Benin Distribution Company (3) Eko Distribution Company (4) Enugu Distribution Company (5) Ibadan Distribution Company (6) Ikeja Distribution Company (7) Jos Distribution Company (8) Kaduna Distribution Company (9) Kano Distribution Company (10) Port Harcourt Distribution Company and (11) Yola Distribution Company.

competition.⁷ The distribution companies in Nigeria have monopoly in the areas allotted to them and often abuse this position by rendering poor, unstable and unreliable electric power supply services resulting in numerous complaints from electricity consumers ranging from inadequate metering, poor maintenance of electricity equipment and installations, issuance of unjustifiable and outrageous estimated bills and illegal disconnection of electricity supply especially without notice. In the second quarter of the year 2023, for instance, electricity consumers made a cumulative of not fewer than three hundred and thirty-three thousand, nine hundred and forty-seven (333,947) complaints to the eleven (11) distribution companies.⁸

Electricity consumers who are not satisfied with the resolution or failure to resolve their complaint by the distribution companies have the option to immediately approach the court or seek further redress from the regulator before seeking redress from regular courts or tribunals. To redress electricity consumer complaints in court or tribunal, identifying the appropriate redress mechanism with jurisdiction is very strategic and an initial stage to a successful remedy. With the current legal framework for electricity consumer protection in Nigeria particularly the Electricity Act, 2023 and the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, there appears to exist at least three (3) courts/tribunals with jurisdiction for redressing electricity consumer disputes: The Federal High Court, the State High Courts and the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT). Though these courts/tribunal are conferred with jurisdiction over electricity consumer protection issues, there appears to be some jurisdictional conflicts when examined against the backdrop of the exclusive jurisdiction conferred on the Federal High Court under section 251(1)(r) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended).

To properly accentuate these issues, this paper is compartmentalised into five parts. The first part is the introduction, the second part is the conceptualisation which forms the building block for the paper. Discussions on the jurisdiction and powers of the Federal High Court, State High Courts and the CCPT in relation to competition and

⁷ Alfred M Tijah, 'Periscoping Competition in the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry' *U.I Law Journal* (2023) (13) 192.

⁸ Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), Third Quarter 2023 Reports, 57.

consumer protection are undertaken under part three. Part four examines the enforcement of consumer rights, while the last part is the conclusion.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATION

This paper used a number of legal terminologies, However, at least three main concepts stand out more clearly and are apposite for a better understanding of the topic under consideration. They are ‘electricity consumer,’ ‘jurisdiction’ and ‘complaint.’

2.1 Electricity Consumer

The term ‘consumer’ includes anyone who consumes goods or services at the end of the chain of production.⁹ It is also defined under section 167 of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018 to ‘include any person who purchase goods otherwise than for the purpose of resale but does not include a person who purchases any goods for the purpose of using them in the production or manufacture of any other goods or articles for sale; or that a service is rendered.’¹⁰ The Electricity Act 2023 on its part defines ‘consumer’ as follows:

Consumer means any end-user of electricity who is a customer of a distribution licensee that is not an eligible customer and, for purposes of filing a complaint with the Commission and for any other reason that the Commission may determine, a person who is temporally disconnected or otherwise without service, provided that a person who has applied for, but has yet to receive, service shall also be deemed to be a consumer.¹¹

The law did not expressly define the concept ‘electricity consumer,’ however from the context, the Electricity Act 2023 actually proffers a definition of the concept ‘electricity consumer.’ The definition of electricity consumer under the Electricity Act 2023 connotes a person registered as an end user of electricity by a Distribution Company (DISCO).¹² In the case of *Mujaid v Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC)*

⁹ *Morgan Stanley Mutual Fund v Kartick Das* (1994) SCC (4) 225.

¹⁰ FCCPA, 2018, s167 (1).

¹¹ Electricity Act, 2023 s232.

¹² Alfred M Tijah and Friday Okpanachi Ekpa, ‘A Jurisprudential Examination of the Status of Successor Companies Under Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry’ *Journal of Private and Property Law, Rivers State University* (2023)(20)(1) 4.

and Ors.,¹³ the Court of Appeal also appear to hold that an electricity consumer means a registered user of electricity. The facts of the case were that it was the Plaintiff/Appellant's landlord that applied to the Respondent, Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company for the connection of the building in issue to the electricity network. The electricity connection to the premises was subsequently disconnected and the appellant been aggrieved brought an action against the Respondent. The court dismissed his action and held that the landlord who actually registered the premises was the consumer and thus the appellant did not have the standing to sue. From the position of the law, an electricity consumer is therefore a registered user of electricity.

2.2 Jurisdiction

In the legal circle, jurisdiction is a notorious concept usually employed to connote the authority which a Court or Tribunal has to decide matters that are litigated before it or take cognizance of matters presented in a formal way for its decision.¹⁴ It is the general power to exercise authority over persons and things within a particular territory. Jurisdiction is a threshold matter, because it is very fundamental as it goes to the competence of the court to hear and determine a suit. Once a court lacks jurisdiction, a party cannot use any statutory provision or common law principle to impose jurisdiction on it because absence of jurisdiction is irreparable in law.¹⁵ Jurisdiction is the basis of any adjudication and without it, any proceeding, judgment or order, is a nullity and liable to be set aside on appeal. It is so fundamental that whenever the issue of jurisdiction is raised, it must be determined before any other issue.¹⁶ The Supreme Court of Nigeria succinctly emphasised the importance of jurisdiction in the case of *Aba v Board of Directors, NIPOST*¹⁷ as follows:

The issue of jurisdiction is fundamental to the court's power to adjudicate. It is the lifeblood of every suit filed in court. Without it, the action would naturally suffocate and die. It is the stamp of authority which inures to the court to entertain a matter. That is

¹³ (2020) LPELR-49740 (CA).

¹⁴ *Mobil Production Nigeria Limited v. Lagos State Environmental Protection Agency & Ors* (2002) 14 SCM 167 at 179 (SC); *Musaconi Limited v Aspinall* (2013) LPELR-20745 (SC); *Saraki v FRN* (2016) LPELR-40013 (SC).

¹⁵ *Umanah v Attah* (2006) 17 NWLR (pt. 1009) 503. *KLM Airtines v Kumzlu* (2004) 8 NWLR (pt. 875) 231; *Obiweubi v CBN* (2011) 7 NWLR (pt. 1247) 465.

¹⁶ *SPDCN Ltd v Oruambo* (2023) NWLR (pt. 1866) 433 at 469, paras. D-F (SC).

¹⁷ (2023) 5 NWLR (pt. 1878) 475 at 493 paras. B-D (SC).

why it can be raised at any stage of the proceedings and even at the Supreme Court for the first time. It can be raised orally or by the court *suo motu*. This is because no matter how well the proceedings are conducted, it would amount to a nullity and a complete waste of time if the court lacked the jurisdiction to entertain the matter.

The jurisdiction of a court to entertain and adjudicate over a matter, action, or appeal, as the case may be, is a matter of strict and hard law which can neither be presumed nor acquiesced to by parties or assumed by the court without express provisions of law.¹⁸ Courts or Tribunals are creations of the Constitution or statutes. The source of jurisdiction exercisable by court or tribunals is therefore conferred and limited by the Constitution or Statute creating them and/or any other relevant statute.¹⁹ Where the Constitution or statutes do not clothe a court with jurisdiction over a matter, neither the court itself nor parties before it can confer jurisdiction on the court to adjudicate over such a matter whatever the nature, be it an application, a suit, or an appeal.²⁰ The law does not permit or allow a court to arrogate and vest itself the jurisdiction that is not statutorily conferred on it over a matter.²¹ The Supreme Court of Nigeria in the *locus classicus* on jurisdiction, *Madukolu v Nkemdilim*,²² held that a court is only competent to exercise jurisdiction on a cause or matter when:

it is properly constituted as regards numbers and qualifications of the members of the bench and no member is disqualified for one reason or another; the subject matter of the case is within its jurisdiction; the case comes before the Court initiated by due process of law; and upon fulfilment of any condition precedent to the exercise of jurisdiction.²³

2.3 Complaint

¹⁸ *Adeyemi v Achimu/NDIC* (2023) 1 NWLR (pt. 1866) 583 at 618, paras. B-C (SC).

¹⁹ *Adeyemi v Achimu/NDIC* (2023) 1 NWLR (pt. 1866) 583 at 617, paras B-C (SC); *Obiuweubi v CBN* (2011) 7 NWLR (pt. 1247) 465; *Mohammed v FRN* (2018) LPELR-43908 (SC).

²⁰ *Adeyemi v Achimu/NDIC* (2023) 1 NWLR (pt. 1866) 583 at 640, paras. A-B.

²¹ *AG Lagos State v Dosunmu* (1989) 3 NWLR (pt. 111) 552; *Lufthansa Airlines v Odiese* (2006) 7 NWLR (pt. 978) 34; *Adeyemi v Achimu/NDIC* (2023) 1 NWLR (pt. 1866) 583 at 629-630, paras. H-A.

²² (1962) 2 SCNLR 341.

²³ See also *Obiuweubi v CBN* (2011) LPELR-2185 (SC).

The word ‘complaint’ is distinctively used in civil and criminal law. The Black’s Law Dictionary in the civil law sense defines complaint as the initial pleading or petition that starts a civil action and states the basis for the court’s jurisdiction, the basis for the plaintiff’s claim, and the demand for relief.²⁴ In relation to criminal law, the same dictionary defines complaint to mean a formal charge accusing a person of an offence.²⁵ Generally, a complaint may be said to consist a statement of allegations made on oath or before an appropriate authority. The NERC Consumer Complaint Handling: Standards and Procedures 2006, under regulation 2(6) defines complaint in relation to electricity services as follows:

Complaint means any allegation in writing made by a complainant, which may include but is not restricted to, the following:

- (i) There exists a defect or deficiency in the electricity service provided by the Distribution Licensee
- (ii) An unfair trade practice or a restrictive trade practice undertaken by the Distribution licensee in providing electricity services;
- (iii) The Distribution Licensee has for the electricity services mentioned in the complaint, charged a price in excess of the price fixed by the Commission, for supply of electricity and allied services;
- (iv) The electricity service provided by the Distribution Licensee may be unsafe or hazardous;
- (v) Recovery of expenses incurred in excess of charges approved by the Commission in providing an electric line or electric plant;
- (vi) Any other act that affects the fulfilment of the contractual relation between the customer and the Distribution Licensee;

²⁴ BA Garner and Others, *Black’s Law Dictionary* (9th edn, West Publishing Co. 1999) 279.

²⁵ *Ibid.*

or is in contravention of the provisions of any Order of the Commission or law for the time being in force.²⁶

The above provisions of the NERC Consumer Complaint Handling: Standards and Procedures 2006, did not only attempt a definition of complaint but equally listed a number of issues worthy of complaint in the Nigerian Electricity Supply industry. Electricity consumers are the most unsatisfied set of consumers in Nigeria. The highest number of complaints received by the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission between 2023 and 2024 was from the electricity consumers and specifically concerning issues of overbilling, disregard of metering, transformer problems, and non-adherence to NERC Regulations on disconnection, tariff band classification and energy tapping.²⁷ Electricity consumers in a number of cases made complaints before the court claiming orders for mandamus, reconnection, damages, compensation and injunctive reliefs. For instance, in the case of *Jos Electricity Distribution (JED) Plc v John*²⁸ the respondent, John who was an electricity consumer filed an action against Jos Electricity Distribution Company Plc before the Plateau State High Court seeking an order of mandamus compelling the Distribution Company to reconnect the house of the Plaintiff with electricity; a declaration that the failure of the Company to adhere to the NERC procedure for disconnection is illegal; damages and apology. The Respondent company challenged the action on the ground that a mandamus cannot be issued against it. The Court of Appeal in affirming the decision of the High Court held that an electricity consumer has the right to seek for an order of mandamus to compel a Distribution Company to carry out its duty to reconnect the electricity supply to the consumer's residence.

Also, in the case of *Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) Plc v Landmark University*,²⁹ the respondent and electricity consumer, Landmark University brought an action before the Kwara State High Court and complained that the respondent wrongly reclassified the respondent from consumer category A3 to C3 and acting therefrom to impose an outrageous bill and as well disconnected the

²⁶ NERC Consumer Complaint Handling: Standards and Procedures 2006, regulation 2(6).

²⁷ News Agency of Nigeria, 'FCCPC Tasks Electricity Distribution Companies on Quick Responses to Customers' Complaints' (2 March, 2024) < FCCPC tasks electricity distribution companies on quick responses to customers' complaints (gazettengr.com) > accessed 24 May, 2024.

²⁸ (2018) LPELR-46395 (CA).

²⁹ (2021) LPELR-56123 (CA)

electricity supply of the consumer and thus sought declarations, injunction and damages against the Distribution Company. The trial court granted the reliefs sought by the plaintiff. However, the Court of Appeal quashed the judgment of the High Court on the ground that the Appellant in the suit is an incompetent party, being a non-juristic person having been sued as Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) instead of the legal name of the Appellant which is ‘Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company Plc.’

3.0 JURISDICTION FOR REDRESSING ELECTRICITY CONSUMER COMPLAINTS

Jurisdiction is a matter of law that is not left to custom, speculation or conjecture. For consumer disputes, aggrieved consumers are permitted by the FCCP Act 2018 to directly approach the court with appropriate jurisdiction for the enforcement of consumer rights.³⁰ The High Court is generally the superior court of record on contractual transactions on which consumer/producer relationship falls under. In addition to the adjudicatory powers of the courts, the FCCP Act created the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT) and conferred upon it jurisdiction for the enforcement of competition and consumer rights.³¹ The FCCP Act did not grant exclusive jurisdiction to any court or tribunal to determine or enforce issues pertaining to or relating to competition and consumer protection. From the provisions of the FCCP Act 2018, therefore the Federal High Court, States High Court and the CCPT all have concurrent jurisdiction on electricity consumer rights violation subject however to the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) and the Statutes establishing these courts or tribunal.

3.1 Jurisdiction of the Federal High Court in Redressing Power Consumer Complaint

There is in every State in Nigeria and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja a division of Federal High Court. Therefore, there are at least thirty-seven (37) Federal High Courts in Nigeria. However, as held in the case of *Roda v FRN*³² the Federal High Court is a single court for the entire Nigeria, and its judicial divisions are mere branches of the

³⁰ FCCP Act, s146(2)

³¹ FCCP Act, s39

³² (2015)10 NWLR (pt. 1468) 427 (SC).

Court. The Federal High Court was originally established in 1973 as the Federal Revenue Court.³³ Its name was changed to the present Federal High Court in 1976 and was first included into the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1979 as a superior court of record.

The Federal High Court of Nigeria is a court of enumerated jurisdiction established pursuant to the provisions of section 249 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended). Its civil and criminal jurisdiction to the exclusion of other courts/tribunal is clearly enumerated under section 251 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended). By the provisions of section 251(1)(r) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended), the Federal High Court has exclusive original jurisdiction to entertain any action or proceeding for a declaration or injunction affecting the validity of any executive or administrative action or decision by the Federal Government or any of its agencies.³⁴ Its jurisdiction equally extends to any action for damages, injunction or specific performance based on any enactment, law or equity initiated by a person seeking redress against the Federal Government or any of its agencies.³⁵

Before the unbundling and privatisation of the power sector and while NEPA as a Federal Government agency had monopoly over the electric power sector, section 251(1)(r) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended) operated to confer exclusive jurisdiction on the Federal High Court to entertain any complaint by electricity consumer against NEPA as a service provider for loss, damage or inconveniences caused to electricity consumers through any suspension, failure, discontinuance or partial interruptions of the supply of electricity.³⁶ For instance in *NEPA v. Auwal*³⁷ the apex court held that by virtue of section 251(1)(r) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended), the Federal High Court has the exclusive jurisdiction to entertain an action for negligence against NEPA and that complaints against the act of disconnecting electricity supply fits into the kind of action that the Federal High Court had exclusive jurisdiction to entertain under section

³³ Federal Revenue Court Decree No. 13 of 1973.

³⁴ Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 (as amended), s251(1)(r).

³⁵ CFRN 1999, s251(1) proviso.

³⁶ Though NEPA was immune from such liabilities under section 12 of the NEPA Act 1990. Section 2(2) however granted immunity only in respect of the no-light and low voltage cases. NEPA was therefore not protected where the damage complained of was a result of high voltage.

³⁷ (2022) LPELR-59473(SC).

251(1)(r) of the 1999 Constitution in that it is an action for a declaration affecting the validity of the executive or administrative action or decision of the agency.

However, with the privatisation of the Nigerian electricity supply industry, the Federal High Court no longer has exclusive jurisdiction over the power sector. The jurisdiction to hear and determine complaint by electricity consumer against the unbundled and privatised successor companies has become vested in the High Court of the States and the High Court of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, being a dispute arising from a transaction of a private business undertaking. This was the position of the court in the case of *NERC and Ors v Tebite and Ors*.³⁸ The facts of the case were that, 1st-7th Respondents were electricity consumers of Benin Electricity Distribution Co. (BEDC) Plc the 2nd Appellant, who was the distributor of electricity within the core area of Asaba. The 3rd Appellant as an agent of the BEDC Plc disconnected the electricity supply to all the Respondents. The Respondents were later reconnected to allow for some form of settlement. However, BEDC Plc issued to the Respondents outrageous and unjustifiable electricity bill of over N2,500,000 and on the same date, the 3rd Appellant invaded the premises of the Respondents with a view to compelling the Respondents to pay the bill and threatened disconnection. The Respondents being aggrieved sought from the Federal High Court via a motion *ex parte* an order of interim injunction restraining the Appellants or any of their agents from disconnecting the Respondents pending the hearing and determination of the motion on notice for interlocutory Injunction. The said motion *ex parte* was moved and granted. The 2nd and 3rd Appellants upon being served filed a preliminary objection challenging the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court to entertain the claim over transactions outside Section 251(1) of the 1999 Constitution (as amended). The trial Court after hearing the parties, overruled the Appellants. Dissatisfied, the Appellants filed an appeal at the Court of Appeal for the court to determine whether the Federal High Court lacks the requisite jurisdiction to adjudicate the matter. The Court of Appeal held that: BEDC is a private electricity distribution company who bought the going concern and operations of NEPA through PHCN (Power Holding Company); the issuance of electricity bill to consumers therefore is the normal administration and management of the BEDC. The issue/allegation/act(s) committed by the BEDC and their servants

³⁸ (2022)LPELR-58321(CA).

was held to be based on contractual obligations under the contract for service. This is an action rooted in a case of simple contract. The breach is against the contract of supply of services of energy by the BEDC. Both the parties herein and the subject matter which is a simple contract for services are not within the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court and the Court lacks jurisdiction to entertain contractual matters.³⁹ The court finally held that the claim falls under the exclusive jurisdiction of the State High Court and transferred the suit to the Chief Judge of Delta State for reassignment and speedy conclusion by any Judge of the Delta State High Court.

Though privatisation divested the Federal High Court of the jurisdiction to entertain electricity consumer complaint against electricity distribution companies, nonetheless, the Federal High Court still maintains exclusive jurisdiction over complaints on competition and consumer protection issues which are the responsibilities of the regulators of the power sector like the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) or Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC). For instance, where NERC or FCCPC fosters or fails to arrest an abuse of monopoly or dominant position by the successor companies which adversely affects electricity consumers, a complaint against the regulator as an agency of the Federal Government will fall under the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court. For instance, in the case of *NERC and Ors v Tebite and Ors*⁴⁰ the court held that the Federal High Court will have exclusive jurisdiction where the issue in contention by the respondent electricity consumer concerns complaint against NERC's management and administration of the distribution companies or the oversight management administration by NERC.

However, where the issue does not fall under section 251 of the CFRN 1999; or involve the management or administrative powers of NERC as a regulator, the Federal High Court will not have jurisdiction even where NERC is a party to the action. In *NEPA v Edeghero*⁴¹ the Supreme Court of Nigeria held that section 251(1)(r) of the CFRN raises both subject matter and parties' issues and both factors must co-exist before the

³⁹ See also *Adelekan v Ecu –Line NV* (2006) LPELR-113 (SC).

⁴⁰ (2022) LPELR-58321 (CA).

⁴¹ (2002) 12 SCNJ 173; (2002) All FWLR (pt.139) 1556.

Federal High Court would have and exercise exclusive jurisdiction pursuant to section 251(1) of the Constitution.

3.2 Jurisdiction of State High Court in Redressing Power Consumer Complaint

The High Court of a State or the High Court of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja is a court of unlimited jurisdiction⁴² created pursuant to sections 270 and 255 respectively of the CFRN 1999 (as amended). The concept ‘unlimited jurisdiction’ is however a qualified concept to the extent that Courts are vested with authority to entertain an action within the limits of the authority conferred on the court by the Constitution and statutes including inherent powers of the court.⁴³ The High Court of a State has jurisdiction to hear and determine any civil proceedings in which the existence or extent of a legal right, power, duty, liability, privilege, interest, obligation or claim is in issue or to hear and determine any criminal proceedings involving or relating to any penalty, forfeiture, punishment or other liability in respect of an offence committed by any person subject to the exclusive jurisdiction conferred on other courts by the Constitution and/or other statutes.⁴⁴ This implies that in so far as no other court has exclusive jurisdiction to entertain a particular dispute, such litigious subject matter falls under the jurisdiction of the High Court of a State or the FCT Abuja.

The Federal High Court was divested of exclusive jurisdiction over complaint relating to electricity service as electricity services was no longer the exclusive administrative action of a federal institution in Nigeria since the services hitherto rendered by NEPA, a Federal Government institution were privatised and performed by private establishment under simple contractual agreements to electricity consumers. The jurisdiction consequentially rolled down to the High Court of States including the High Court of the FCT Abuja which have universal and thus default jurisdiction. The provisions of section 146(2) of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act (FCCP Act), 2018 confers on every consumer inclusive of electricity consumer the right to directly approach a court with appropriate jurisdiction for the resolution of any

⁴² *Gafar v Government of Kwara State and Ors* (2007) LPELR-8073 (SC) 38, paras. A-C.

⁴³ *AG Osun State v International Breweries Plc* (2000) LPELR-10094 (CA) 36-37, paras. B-B.

⁴⁴ CFRN 1999 (as amended), s272; *Fagbemi v Omonigbehin and Ors* (2012) LPELR-15359 (CA) 39-40, paras. D-B.

dispute with an undertaking that supplies the goods or services to the consumer. The FCCP Act 2018 thus confers on the High Court the jurisdiction to hear any dispute directly even where an electricity consumer has not first approached a distribution company for the resolution of the dispute in accordance with the regulation of the NERC.

3.3 Jurisdiction of Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal in Redressing Power Consumer Complaint

The Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT) is an agency of Federal Government of Nigeria established pursuant to section 39 of the FCCP Act 2018. The CCPT consists of a chairman and six (6) other members appointed by the President of Nigeria subject to confirmation by the Senate to hold office for a term of five years and no more or upon attainment of 70 years of age.⁴⁵ The Chairman must be a legal practitioner of at least ten (10) years post-call and cognate experience in the field of competition, consumer protection or commercial and industrial law; while the six (6) other members, must have at least ten (10) years professional experience in any one or more of the following educational fields: competition and consumer protection law, commerce and industry, public affairs, economics, finance, or business administration or management.⁴⁶

The CCPT has jurisdiction, powers and authority to adjudicate over issues pertaining to competition and consumer protection in the entirety of Nigeria.⁴⁷ The Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT) is properly constituted with a Panel of at least three members,⁴⁸ and at least one of the three members must possess the requisite legal training, experience and good knowledge of competition and consumer protection matters.⁴⁹ A decision of a Panel of the CCPT must either be unanimous or of a majority of the members of the Panel and shall be in writing and include reasons for the decision.⁵⁰

⁴⁵ FCCP Act, s40 and 41.

⁴⁶ FCCP Act, s40.

⁴⁷ FCCP Act, s39 (2).

⁴⁸ FCCP Act, s48 (2).

⁴⁹ FCCP Act, s48 (3).

⁵⁰ FCCP Act, s48 (6) and (8).

The subject matters within the jurisdiction of the CCPT are issues pertaining to competition and consumer protection from any sector of the Nigerian economy. It has only an appellate jurisdiction and thus the due process of initiating a case before the CCPT is by way of an appeal or review of the decision of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC).⁵¹ The CCPT entertains appeals or reviews emanating only from the decisions of the FCCPC, According to section 47 of the FCCP Act, the CCPT has jurisdiction to hear appeals from or review any decision of the FCCPC taken in the course of the implementation of any of the provisions of the FCCP Act as may be referred to it. The FCCP Act does not stipulate the time limit an aggrieved party may appeal the decision of the FCCPC to the CCPT. This is necessary for expeditious determination of complaint. A provision of time limit for determination of an appeal akin to the 180 days for determination of election petition will engender speedy dispensation of justice to justify the creation of a special tribunal for determining competition and consumer protection issues.

The jurisdiction of the CCPT also extends to appeals from, or the review of any decision from the exercise of powers of any sector specific regulatory authority in a regulated industry in respect of competition and consumer protection matters. This jurisdiction is however not direct but only after the FCCPC have first heard and determined such issue emanating from a sector specific regulator before an appeal may be lodged before the CCPT.⁵² This entails that no decisions from a sector specific regulatory institutions like the NERC, CBN, NCC pertaining to competition and consumer protection shall lie directly to the CCPT unless such decision is heard and determined by the FCCPC. This is a condition precedent which must be fulfilled before the CCPT may assume jurisdiction in any matter before it from a sector specific regulator. In the case of *Orakul Resources Ltd v NCC*,⁵³ the Supreme Court of Nigeria defined ‘condition precedent as follows: ‘a condition precedent is one which must happen or to be performed before the estate to which it is annexed can vest; or it is one which is to be

⁵¹ FCCP Act, s38.

⁵² FCCP Act, s47 (a) and (b).

⁵³ (2022)6 NWLR(pt. 1827) 529 at 586, para. A-C (SC).

performed before some right dependent thereon accrues or some act performed.⁵⁴ The apex court in Nigeria in the *Orakul case* also stated that:

Where the provisions of a statute or law prescribes some internal mechanisms by which remedies or reliefs for some grievance(s) could be sought and to be followed or complied with by a party before instituting a legal action in a court of law over the same grievance(s), the party has no discretion or option, but to exhaust all the remedies provided for by the statute or law first, before going to court as the court's jurisdiction in such circumstance, will be put in abeyance pending the completion of the internal mechanisms for the remedies.⁵⁵

The condition precedent such as the one stipulated under the FCCP Act delays the vesting of a right until the happening of an event⁵⁶ and it is submitted to make the enforcement of competition and consumer protection rights through the CCPT cumbersome and time consuming. The procedure is even more complicated under the Nigerian electricity supply industry. For instance, it is mandatory for an electricity consumer to first table his or her complaint to the distribution company involved through its Customer Complaint Unit (CCU) before escalating the complaint to the NERC Forum.⁵⁷ Under regulation 12(1) of the NERC Consumer Complaint Handling: Standards and Procedures 2006, made by NERC pursuant to section 96 of the EPSR Act any electricity consumer that is aggrieved of a decision made by the NERC Forum may seek appeal against such decision to the NERC within a period of ten (10) working days from the date of the decision by NERC Forum. While the FCCP Act makes it compulsory under section 47 for a dispute emanating from a sector specific regulator like NERC to be entertained by the FCCPC before being filed before the CCPT. Therefore, for an electricity consumer to approach the CCPT, the consumer must first make a complaint to the Distribution Company (DISCO) covering the area; if not satisfied with the actions or inactions of the DISCO, escalate the complaint to the

⁵⁴ See also *IAL 361 Inc v Mobil Nig Plc* (1999) 5 NWLR (pt. 601) 9; *Adeleke v Osaka* (2006) 16 NWLR (pt. 1006) 608; *Niger-Care Dev. Co. Ltd. v Adamawa State Water Bel* (2008) 9 NWLR (pt. 1093) 498; *Dresel Energy and Nat. Res. Ltd v Trans. Int'l Bank Ltd* (2009) 18 NWLR (pt. 1119) 388.

⁵⁵ *Orakul Resources Ltd v NCC* (2022) 6 NWLR (pt. 1827) 529 at 587, para. E-H (SC).

⁵⁶ *Orakul Resources Ltd v NCC* (2022) 6 NWLR (pt. 1827) 529 at 586, para. A (SC).

⁵⁷ *Ibid*, regulation 3 (9).

NERC Forum; then appeal to NERC if still not satisfied, and a further appeal to the FCCPC before the CCPT will have jurisdiction to hear any complaint by the electricity consumer by way of an appeal from the decision of the FCCPC. However, by dint of section 146(2) of the FCCP Act, this lengthy condition precedent must not be followed where a consumer desire to directly approach the court.⁵⁸

The Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT) is imbued with inherent powers like the High Courts to make any rulings or issue such orders as may be necessary or incidental to the performance of its function.⁵⁹ It can thus summon and enforce the attendance of any person, including the power to examine a person under oath; require the discovery and production of documents; call for and examine witnesses under oath; receive evidence on affidavits; and do anything which, in the opinion of the CCPT, is deemed necessary to issue a final and reasoned decision on the merit of the matter before it.⁶⁰

The CCPT also has the powers to impose administrative penalties only for a prohibited practice under the FCCP Act; or the contravention of, or failure to comply with an interim order of the CCPT.⁶¹ An administrative penalty imposed by the CCPT shall not exceed 10% of the undertaking's annual turnover in Nigeria and its exports from Nigeria during the preceding financial year.⁶² When determining an appropriate administrative penalty, the CCPT is required by section 51(3) of the FCCP Act, 2018 to take into consideration the following:

- a) the nature, duration, gravity and extent of the contravention;
- b) any loss or damage suffered as a result of the contravention;
- c) the behaviour of the defaulting party;
- d) the market circumstances in which the contravention took place;
- e) the level of profit derived from the circumstance;
- f) the degree to which the defaulting party has co-operated with the FCCPC and the CCPT; or

⁵⁸ FCCP Act, 2018 s146(2).

⁵⁹ FCCP Act, s47(c) and (d).

⁶⁰ FCCP Act, s50(2).

⁶¹ FCCP Act, s51(1)(a) and (b).

⁶² FCCP Act, s51 (2).

- g) whether the defaulting party has previously been found to be in contravention of any of the provisions of the FCCP Act.⁶³

The Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal (CCPT) equally has powers to order sale of assets. Section 52 of the FCCP Act states that the CCPT may make an order directing any undertaking to sell any portion or all of its shares, interest or assets if the practice prohibited under the FCCP Act cannot adequately be remedied under any other provision of the FCCP Act; or is substantially a repeat by the undertaking of conduct previously found by the CCPT to be a prohibited practice.⁶⁴ The order for sale of assets may provide for time-frame for compliance and any other term that the CCPT considers appropriate, having regard to the commercial interests of the parties concerned.⁶⁵ For the purpose of the enforcement of any order, ruling, award or judgment of the CCPT which is binding against any party before it, the judgment must be registered with the Federal High Court.⁶⁶

Any party to a proceeding before the Tribunal may either appear in person or authorise one or more legal practitioners or any of its officers to represent the party before the Tribunal.⁶⁷ Where a party or its representative is unable for good cause to attend a hearing before the Tribunal, the Tribunal may adjourn the hearing for such reasonable time as it deems fit, or admit the matter to be made by some other person or by way of a written address.⁶⁸

An appeal from the decision of the CCPT by virtue of section 38 and 103 of the FCCP Act shall lie to the Court of Appeal. An aggrieved party is required to file a notice of appeal at the Registry of the CCPT within 30 days after the date on which the ruling, award or judgment was given. And the Registrar to the CCPT shall cause the notice to be given to the Chief Registrar of the Court of Appeal along with the record of proceedings and exhibits tendered at the hearing before the Tribunal.

The FCCP Act seemed to accord the CCPT concurrent jurisdiction with the Federal High Court in matters arising from the administrative action and decision of the

⁶³ FCCP Act, s51 (3).

⁶⁴ FCCP Act, s52 (1).

⁶⁵ FCCP Act, s52 (2).

⁶⁶ FCCP Act, s54 (b).

⁶⁷ FCCP Act, s56 (1).

⁶⁸ FCCP Act, s56 (2).

FCCPC particularly on matters pertaining to competition and consumer protection which constitutionally is under the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court pursuant to section 251 (1)(r) of the Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 (as amended). The section provides that:

251. (1) Notwithstanding anything to the contrary contained in this Constitution and in addition to such other jurisdiction as may be conferred upon it by an Act of the National Assembly, the Federal High Court shall have and exercise jurisdiction to the exclusion of any other court in civil causes and matters –

(r) any action or proceeding for a declaration or injunction affecting the validity of any executive or administrative action or decision by the Federal Government or any of its agencies.

Provided that nothing in the provisions of paragraphs (p), (q) and (r) of this subsection shall prevent a person from seeking redress against the Federal Government or any of its agencies in an action for damages, injunction or specific performance where the action is based on any enactment, law or equity.

The Supreme Court in a plethora of decisions have elaborately interpreted the above provisions and the proviso. For instance, in the *locus classicus* on the issue, *NEPA v Edeghero*⁶⁹ the Supreme Court of Nigeria held that, the proper or only court of original civil jurisdiction to try an administrative or management decision of an agency of the Federal Government is the Federal High Court.

The blanket jurisdiction conferred on the CCPT by sections 38, 47, 67(3), 86(2) and 103 of the FCCP Act is unconstitutional and an incursion into the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court as provided under section 251(1)(r) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended) since the CCPT is accorded jurisdiction over the executive or administrative actions or decisions of the FCCPC, as an agency of the Federal Government of Nigeria. The CCPT not being one of the Superior Courts of Record under section 6 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria cannot take over or share the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court unless with express provisions of the

⁶⁹ (2002)12 SCNJ 176; (2003) FWLR (pt. 139)1556.

Constitution. In the case of *National Union of Electricity Employees v Bureau of Public Enterprises*⁷⁰ the Supreme Court held that though the National Assembly has power to create new courts, the respondent has conceded that the National Assembly by dint of section 6(4) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) has the power to create courts but of subordinate jurisdiction to the High Court, and that the exercise of such powers cannot affect or derogate from the jurisdiction of the High Court on the matters within the jurisdictional competence of the High Court. However, the National Assembly intends to create court as a Superior Court of Record that can affect the jurisdictional competence of the High Court, it can only properly do so with an amendment of Section 6(3) and (5) of the Constitution which has exhaustively listed all the Superior Courts of Record known under the Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended).⁷¹

The provision of section 1(3) of the Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) prohibits the existence of any other law that is inconsistent with its provision and declares that such other law shall be void to the extent of its inconsistency with the Constitution. By virtue of section 1(1) and (3) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended), the Constitution is supreme and its provisions shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The Supreme Court clearly held in the case of *Nwokedi v Anambra State Government*⁷² that where any other law is inconsistent with the provisions of the Constitution, the Constitution shall prevail and that other law shall to the extent of the inconsistency be void. A law enacted in excess of the powers granted by the Constitution is void to the extent of the inconsistency with the provision of the Constitution.⁷³ The substratum of a court is jurisdiction which is the court's fiat or stamp of authority to adjudicate. It is very important in the adjudicatory process. Without it, the proceedings of the court involving the litigants, counsel and judge are in vain.⁷⁴ Since the provisions of the FCCP Act which is the source of the jurisdiction of the CCPT are inconsistent with the provisions of the CFRN 1999 (as amended), the exercise of authority by the CCPT in

⁷⁰ (2010)7 NWLR (pt 1194)538.

⁷¹ See also on the same principle the case of *Attorney General of Oyo State v Nigeria Labour Congress* (2003)8 NWLR (Pt. 821)1 at 3.

⁷² *Nwokedi v Anambra State Government* (2022) 7 NWLR (pt. 1828) 29 at 67-68, paras. F-B (SC).

⁷³ *Nwokedi v Anambra State Government* (2022) 7 NWLR (pt. 1828) 29 at 67-68, paras. F-B (SC).

⁷⁴ *PTF v Fidelity Bank Plc* (2022) 9 NWLR (pt. 1836)475 at 510, paras D-F (SC).

resolving electricity consumer issues may come to naught since the Tribunal is devoid of jurisdictional competence.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The court is the foremost formal adjudicatory and enforcement institution of civil and criminal disputes. It is the last hope of the common man and thus plays an essential role in the protection of electricity consumers. The Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, which is the most comprehensive and supreme statute regulating competition and consumer protection in Nigeria subject however, to the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) did not confer exclusive jurisdiction on any particular court or tribunal to hear and determine cases relating to competition and consumer protection. Although the FCCP Act 2018 provide for a condition requiring consumers to first make an attempt at resolving their disputes with the undertaking that supplied goods or services to the consumer and resort to the sector specific regulator, the FCCP Act 2018 further water down this condition precedent by granting aggrieved consumers the liberty to directly approach a court with appropriate jurisdiction for the enforcement of any consumer right notwithstanding the condition precedent.⁷⁵ The adjudicatory jurisdiction for redressing electricity consumer complaints is therefore not exclusively vested in a single adjudicatory body but hovers mainly around three courts/tribunal: the Federal High Court, States High Courts and the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal. Though these courts and tribunal have concurrent jurisdiction, there is some distinction as to the extent of the jurisdiction exercised.

The Federal High Court being court of enumerated jurisdiction only has powers in this regard to determine issues relating to the validity of administrative decision or action of the Federal Government or any of its regulatory agencies like the NERC and the FCCPC on matters pertaining to competition and consumer protection affecting the rights of electricity consumers. The High Courts of States, being courts of unlimited jurisdiction have jurisdiction to hear and determine all litigious consumer complaint except those exclusively within the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court. The Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal only has an appellate jurisdiction

⁷⁵ FCCP Act s146 (1) and (2).

limited to consumer complaints concerning competition and consumer protection emanating from the administrative action or decisions of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission. The jurisdiction of the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal is therefore a usurpation of the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court.

Among the three courts, the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal as a special court with a streamlined jurisdiction is most likely to expeditiously determine case before it, however, while consumers can directly approach either the Federal High Court or the High Court of a State/Federal Capital Territory to redress electricity consumer complaint, no electricity consumer can directly approach the CCPT as a court/tribunal of first instance. For the CCPT to be vested with the requisite jurisdiction to entertain an electricity consumer complaint, the consumer must have first redressed the issue and remained unsatisfied at the Consumer Complaint Unit of electricity Distribution Company, escalate the complaint to the NERC Consumer Forum, then the NERC, and further to the FCCPC before approaching the CCPT.

It is therefore recommended that, section 6 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) should be further amended to crystallise the jurisdiction of the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal over competition and consumer protection issues by elevating the Tribunal to the status of a Superior Court of Record with original civil and criminal jurisdiction to entertain competition and consumer protection cases. Also recommended is the removal of the condition precedent requiring the determination of any complaint by the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission and other sector specific regulatory institution before the Tribunal is swathe with jurisdiction. This will streamline the adjudicatory process for speedy dispensation of justice.